

ANALYZING MAFIC ROCKS AND THEIR INTERACTIONS WITH HOST
GRANODIORITE IN THE JACKASS LAKES PLUTON OF THE CENTRAL SIERRA
NEVADA BATHOLITH

by

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Abstract

The intrusion of mafic magmas has often been interpreted to trigger volcanic eruptions. Thus, understanding interactions between mafic and felsic magmas in plutons is important.

The 175 km², 98-97 Ma Jackass Lakes pluton (JLP) in the central Sierra Nevada batholith, a slightly older pluton just south of the 1,100 km², 95-85 Ma Tuolumne intrusive complex, is compositionally more heterogeneous at map- to outcrop-scale. It is largely composed of compositionally varying equigranular to porphyritic granodiorites. In addition, cm- to several km-long quartz diorite bodies are found across the JLP. McNulty et al. (1996) suggested that these mafic magmas represent dikes or sheets, while Pignotta et al. (2010) proposed that they occur in irregular shapes and mixed/mingled with host magmas.

This study analyzed seventeen mafic rock samples from map-scale bodies to cm-scale enclaves from the NW- central JLP with petrography, Cathodoluminescence (CL) imaging, plagioclase extinction angle analysis to determine anorthite content, and XRF whole rock major and trace element analyses to examine 1) if these mafic magmas are compositionally homogeneous and likely derived from the same source, and 2) to what degree they interacted with host granodiorites.

Most mafic rock outcrops observed in the study area occur in cm- to m-scale irregular bodies made of quartz diorite. Of the four observed granodioritic host phases, only the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj) and the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr) showcase the occurrence of mafic enclaves. Petrography has revealed that of the five most prominent minerals typical in intermediate granitoids, quartz varies the most with a range of 3-30%, with hornblende and plagioclase feldspar being tied as the second most varied mineral with their respective ranges of 14-40% and 29-55%. Most samples are porphyritic, with plagioclase, quartz, and alkali feldspar making up most phenocrysts (the latter two likely deriving from the granodioritic host). Plagioclase varies most in grain size (0.20-20 mm) and forms sizeable clusters. Sericitized plagioclase cores indicate higher An-content derived from earlier, more mafic magmas. Five samples were selected for plagioclase extinction angle analysis due to their encompassment of the primary observed mafic units across the three sampling regions (Figs. 6, 9-10), with two associated granodioritic host phase samples undergoing the same analysis for comparison. The plagioclase grains of the five mafic samples showcase an average anorthite content range of 40-45% whereas the two host samples showcase values of 13.5 and 25.5% respectively, indicating

that the plagioclase grains of the mafic bodies are closer in composition to one another than those of the granodioritic host phases. This apparent homogeneity across plagioclase compositions alludes to the mafic samples all potentially sharing a magmatic source.

In CL, the mafic samples appear homogeneous in regard to zoning, along with the mineral distribution of the three observed samples reflecting the modal abundances calculated via petrographic analysis. An observable contact between two units in one thin section is relatively sharp, with minimal transfer of plagioclase grains occurring between the units. While said observation suggests minimal mixing/mingling with the surrounding host granodiorite units, the irregular plagioclase zoning observed in a third sample indicates magma (crystal and melt) mixing with the host granodiorite. Magma mixing as part of the mingling process between the mafic bodies/enclaves and the host granodiorites is further supported by XRF whole rock major and trace element analysis. While the mineral abundances point towards compositionally relatively homogenous mafic rocks, the varied distribution of some major and trace elements such as CaO, FeO, MgO, Ba, Zr, and Sr point towards heterogeneity among the mafic magmas. Such heterogeneity can be explained by minor mineral abundance variations caused by fractional crystallization, magma mixing and mingling at the emplacement level and during magma ascent, and some potential heterogeneities present in the source.

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2. Introduction

While volcanic systems play very critical roles in various aspects of society, studying active systems proves difficult due to the multiple dangers they impose. Such dangers include but are not limited to toxic gas emissions, pyroclastic flows, and high temperatures. To avoid such dangers, it is ideal to study the structure of inactive systems, so as to determine the structure, history, and potential evolution of active systems. Specifically, studies should be conducted at denudated plutonic rocks when attempting to analyze aspects such as the construction and evolution of magma plumbing systems under volcanoes, as the deeper parts of systems are not exposed in active systems and are difficult to access even in some inactive systems. Perhaps one of the best locations to do so is the Jackass Lakes Pluton of the Sierra Nevada Batholith (Fig. 1), as its exposure and good vertical relief enables detailed examination of various attributes, such as magmatic compositions and interactions with different magmas, magmatic structures, ages, and pluton-host rock relationships (Pignotta et al. 2010). The Sierra Nevada Batholith is part of a large Cordilleran magmatic arc that ranges from Alaska to Mexico. Its formation dates back to the Mesozoic when the Farallon plate subducted under the North American Plate (Krueger and Yoshinobu, 2018).

One of the more under-researched aspects of the JLP is the petrology of the different magmatic units and the interactions between various mafic and felsic magmas of the JLP. This attribute in particular serves to provide a more detailed history of both the JLP's formation and evolution through time, as well as of the history of the surrounding parts of the Sierra Nevada Batholith. For instance, whereas the majority of plutons in the Sierra Nevada Batholith are primarily composed of large homogenous igneous units, with a prime example being the Tuolumne intrusion (Bateman 1992; Memeti et al., 2021), the JLP is more varied in its composition at much smaller scales, containing granodiorites, diorites, granites, and leucogranites (Pignotta et al., 2010). From this, it is possible to deduce that the environment (i.e. the magma chamber) the JLP developed in differed from that of most plutons in the Sierra Nevada Batholith. Furthermore, many volcanic studies suggest that the introduction of mafic magmas into more silicic magmas can be a cause for remobilization of the more viscous, felsic magmas and thus volcanic eruptions. As such, more emphasis should be placed on studying interactions between mafic and felsic magmas in the pluton, as such a detail could help provide

new information regarding the pluton's structural evolution and interaction with the surrounding rock.

3. Background

The JLP is a composite intrusion located in the central region of the Sierra Nevada Batholith and is recorded to be 97-98 Ma (Fig. 1; Bateman, 1992; McNulty et al., 1996; Pignotta et al., 2010; Krueger and Yoshinobu, 2018). While the pluton as a whole spans roughly 13 by 17 km, it is divided into four lobes by slightly older metavolcanic and plutonic pendants (Fig. 2; Pignotta et al., 2010). At the moment there have been three models made in an attempt to explain the emplacement and temporal evolution of the JLP. The first model was proposed in a paper by McNulty et al. (1996) and revolves around the premise that the JLP was assembled via vertical diking or sheeting, was not tilted, and that pluton growth was achieved via downward return flow along the margins of the pluton. The second model was proposed by Wiebe (1999, 2000), in which they note that the present subvertical mafic sheets represent multiple gently dipping floors formed in a magma chamber that were rotated to their present dips. The third model was developed by Pignotta et al. (2010) and proposes that the initial magma emplacement involved sheeted intrusion and diking, which heated and subsequently weakened the host rock, enabling it to become host rock for greater amounts of irregular shaped magma increments. In addition, they emphasize the fact that magmatic pulses hybridized and mingled extensively.

Perhaps the most notable mafic attributes found in the JLP are mafic dikes (Fig. 3) and mafic sheets (Fig. 4). In general, mafic dikes and mafic sheets are extremely similar, with the most discernable differences between them being that a dike is defined as an intrusion formed by the transport of magma via a propagating crack, whereas a sheet is an intrusion with a length/width ratio between 10 and 100 that is formed by processes of ductile deformation and elements of dike-like behavior (Pignotta et al., 2010). A notable distinction is the fact that the sheets can have gradational contacts with the host magma and indicate variable degrees of hybridization and mingling. In addition to this, the mafic dikes and mafic sheets also slightly vary in orientation in the JLP, with the dikes being subvertical and north-to-northwest striking whereas the sheets are simply northwest-southeast oriented (McNulty et al., 1996; Pignotta et al., 2010). The mafic dikes are also divided into subcategories depending on the relative timing they intruded into the JLP. They are classified as either early, synchronous, or late phase dikes

(McNulty et al., 1996). In regard to composition, the mafic dikes and sheets are extremely similar to one another, with both of them being composed of diorite and quartz diorite (McNulty et al., 1996; Pignotta et al., 2010).

The bulk composition of the JLP pluton is primarily granodiorite. While the exact composition of the granodioritic units varies in some sections of the JLP, on average it is light gray in coloration, and coarse-to-medium grained. As a granodiorite, its essential rock forming minerals include quartz, alkali feldspar, and plagioclase feldspar. It is recognized for containing roughly 10% biotite and smaller amounts of hornblende, along with accessory minerals such as apatite, zircon, titanite, and muscovite (Bateman, 1992; Krueger and Yoshinobu, 2018). The chilled margins evident in the late-phase dikes indicate their intrusion after the bulk crystallization of the granodioritic host, but the back-veining evident in the same late-phase dikes by the host implies that at the time of intrusion, at least some portion of the granodioritic host was still in a magmatic state (McNulty et al., 1996). In relation to the host rock of other nearby magmatic systems, the JLP intruded the dark, medium-grained, equigranular hornblende-biotite granodiorite and hornblende tonalite of Illilouette Creek of the intrusive suite of the Buena Vista Crest, which has a discordant U-Pb age of 100 Ma. It is intruded by the medium-grained equigranular hornblende-biotite granodiorite and granite of Ostrander Lake and Breeze Lake, which also belong to the intrusive suite of Buena Vista Crest and has two discordant U-Pb ages of 112 and 107 Ma (Bateman, 1992). It is also intruded by the mafic hornblende-biotite granodiorite of Red Devil Lake and porphyritic biotite granite of Turner Lake, which belong to the intrusive suite of Washburn Lake and has a concordant U-Pb age of 98 Ma (Fig. 5; Bateman, 1992; Peck, 1980).

In addition to said intrusions, another attribute the JLP is known for is its high concentration of volcanic pendants and xenoliths, the first of which are generally elongated parallel to the mineral and enclave foliation in the JLP, and the second occur commonly near pendants but can be found all throughout the pluton (Peck, 1980; McNulty et al., 1996; Pignotta et al., 2010). Notably, the JLP is also recognized for attributes such as its hybrid units, which have high enclave and enclave swarm density, even when compared to other JLP units, which all are recognized for being packed with enclaves and enclave swarms (Pignotta et al., 2010).

4. Statement of Purpose

The primary purpose of this project is to collect petrologic, compositional, and spatial data pertaining to mafic magmas present in the JLP with the aim to gain a better understanding of the magmatic environment present in the JLP during and after their intrusion. Given that the petrology and evolution through time of the magmatic system of the pluton have been generally unobserved, emphasis was placed on analyzing the composition of the former mafic magmas, their degree of compositional variance, and the various ways in which the mafic magmas may have interacted with the surrounding host granodiorite of the JLP.

5. Research Rationale

While the mechanisms behind the construction of the JLP have been studied by previous workers (Peck, 1980; McNulty et al., 1996; Pignotta et al., 2010; Krueger and Yoshinobu, 2016), the petrologic evolution of the JLP is relatively unknown. Given that the JLP is perhaps one of the most well-preserved and well-exposed inactive systems (next to the Tuolumne intrusion in Yosemite National Park), it serves as one of the best sites to study how active systems in similar environments operate at depth and may help mitigate volcanic hazards. Furthermore, in addition to serving as a basis for understanding active magmatic systems, additional research on the evolution of arc plutonic arcs can increase our understanding of the development of continental crust (Coleman and Glazner, 1997).

6. Goals

The goals of this study are to:

- Denote patterns of occurrence of mafic outcrops within the JLP and its various phases.
- Determine if there are any compositional variations notable enough between the mafic outcrops to allude to multiple magma storage regions.
- Identify any mineralogical and geochemical patterns between the various mafic outcrops that allude to a shared magma storage region and compositional variations.
- Compare the compositions of plagioclase feldspar in the mafic outcrops to that of the granodioritic host.
- Identify any mineralogical and geochemical variations between samples that imply the occurrence of magma mingling/mixing with the granodiorite host rock.

7. Research Hypothesis

I hypothesize that all mafic magmas present in the JLP originated from the same magma storage region and represent different degrees of activity and mingling with the granodioritic host.

8. Methods

8.1. Field Observations

Field work was conducted over the course of four weeks alongside multiple graduate and undergraduate students in the summer of 2022. Stations and their associated samples utilized in this study were derived from the marked graduate mapping region, undergraduate mapping region, and the sizeable Kqd outcrop located to the south of both regions (Figs. 6, 9-10). Observations made at each station, such as the presence and abundance of enclaves, modal abundances, grain size, rock name, strike/dip measurements, magmatic fabric measurements, nearby unit contacts and other such observations were recorded in a Rite-in-the-Rain field book.

Coordinates of all stations were recorded with handheld GPS units set to UTM Datum Nad Con 1927 (Table 1) and plotted on the respective graduate and undergraduate maps (Figs. 9-10). A Brunton Compass was used to make strike and dip measurements of magmatic fabrics. Most of the other observations were made via the use of a hand lens. Of the various samples collected from the field, 17 were derived from mafic outcrops and utilized for analysis in this study.

8.2. Petrography

The 17 mafic samples were utilized to make 18 thin sections, with one sample, SM 156, serving as the source for two thin sections due to macroscopically obvious variations in composition. Through the utilization of the CSUF geology department's water trim saw, the samples were cut into 1cm thick 27x46 billets, which were then sent to Precision Petrographics in Vancouver, Canada, to be made into uncovered thin sections that would go on to be used for petrographic analysis, plagioclase composition analysis, and cathodoluminescence microscopy. All petrographic work, such as mineral assemblages and textures were conducted via the use of a Nikon LV-100 POL petrographic microscope in Dr. Vali Memeti's dry lab. Observations pertaining to microstructures were in part made based on the respective descriptions and illustrations detailed in Vernon (2004) and Browne (2007).

8.3. Plagioclase Composition

Five mafic samples were used to determine average plagioclase feldspar composition values via the Michel Lévy method as detailed in Nesse (2000). Ten plagioclase feldspar grains within each thin section were selected for their clear showcasing of albite twinning under cross-polarized light. Each grain was centered under the petrographic microscope's view and rotated until its albite twinning was at its most apparent. Following this, each grain would be rotated counterclockwise until its first extinction angle was achieved, which was denoted by the black and white twinning pattern transitioning to a uniform grey across the grain. Once the first extinction angle was determined for each grain, the second extinction angle was determined by repeating the process but instead rotating the grain clockwise (Fig. 7). When two extinction angles were determined for each grain, the two values were averaged out to yield one extinction angle value per grain. Once ten plagioclase grains in each thin section had an assigned plagioclase extinction angle value, the highest extinction angle value was elected to represent the thin section. The five thin section's maximum extinction angle values were then plugged into a diagram that correlates the albite twinning extinction angle with the percentage of anorthite present in the plagioclase feldspar (Fig. 8), yielding the average anorthite composition present in the plagioclase feldspar of each thin section. This process was repeated with samples from the granodioritic host subunits for comparison with the values derived from the five mafic thin sections.

8.4. Cathodoluminescence (CL) Microscopy

A Nikon SMZ18 Microscope with a CITL attachment in Dr. Memeti's dry lab was used to create CL images of thin sections derived from mafic outcrops. In the end, only three thin sections were selected to undergo CL microscopy. The process of CL imaging involved placing each thin section in the microscope's vacuum-sealed chamber and bombarding it with electrons. The presence of certain elements within the minerals in the thin section excited electrons and released photons with distinct wavelengths upon their return to low-energy orbitals. The distinct wavelengths are dependent on mineral type and the elements present in them, which results in each mineral having its own distinct color in the CL images, with a reddish-pink coloration indicating sodic plagioclase, a greenish-blue coloration indicating more calcic plagioclase, dark purple indicating quartz, gold indicating apatite, and blue indicating alkali feldspar. Minerals

such as hornblende, biotite, hematite, and magnetite appear black due to their lack of luminescence. Emphasis was placed on using coloration differences to identify zoning patterns in plagioclase feldspar that correlate with changes in melt composition.

8.5. XRF Whole Rock Data Analysis

All seventeen mafic outcrop samples were subjected to XRF whole rock data analysis. All granodioritic samples from the associated graduate and undergraduate mapping regions were also subjected to XRF analysis and utilized in this study for comparison. The processes of preparing glass beads to be used for XRF analysis was conducted in accordance with procedures described in Johnson et al. (1999). Preparation began with cutting chunks of each sample via the use of the CSUF department's water trim saw. Said chunks were then crushed into smaller fragments via the CSUF department's jaw crusher before finally being reduced into jars of fine powder via the use of a shatter box. The powdered samples were then mixed with dilithium tetraborate flux at a 1:2 ratio. Specifically, $3.500\text{g} \pm .0004$ of each sample were mixed with $7.000\text{g} \pm .0004$ of flux and then homogenized via the use of a Geni Vortex in Dr. Memeti's dry lab. The mixtures were then emptied out into graphite crucibles, which were then heated in the CSUF department's furnace at $1,000^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 minutes to make glass beads out of the powder. Once the initial batch of beads were finished and given time to cool, each bead was removed from its container, reduced to powder via the shatter box, and then fused once again to ensure homogeneity in each bead. Once the second batch of beads was ready, they were all engraved with their respective sample names via the use of a Dremel tool. The undersides of the beads were then polished with sandpaper with increasingly fining grits progressing from 400 to 600 to finally 2000. Once the bead preparations were finalized, they were sent over to Pomona College to undergo analysis via their X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometer. All geochemical data subsequently yielded was plotted using the free online software, GCD Kit (<http://www.gcdkit.org/>). Interpretations of the resulting major oxide and trace element plots were in part made with respect to Rollinson (1993).

9. Results

9.1. Field Observations

9.1.1. Overview

Among the four granodioritic host phases, only the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj) and the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr) contain mafic enclaves. The Jackass Lakes Anne Lake phase (Kja) and the Jackass Lakes Fernandez Pass phase (Kjf) both lack the occurrence of mafic enclaves. Mafic enclaves located within the metavolcanic blocks (Km) are derived from Kjr dikes within the Km unit rather than directly occurring within the Km unit. Similarly, mafic bodies within/in close association with the Post Peak leucogranite porphyry unit (Kpp) are composed of mafic rock from the quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd). Contrary to observations made in Pignotta et al. (2010) and McNulty et al. (1996) in their respective mapping areas, none of the observed mafic bodies in our mapping regions occur as mafic dikes or sheets. Instead, they occur primarily as enclave swarms, with the enclaves being irregular in shape and varying in size from only a few millimeters at the smallest to a few meters at the largest. All mafic samples collected are grey to dark grey in coloration. While there are a few exceptions, almost all samples are porphyritic quartz diorite, with some plagioclase phenocrysts clearly visible in most hand samples without the need of any magnification.

All seventeen samples were collected for this study over the course of four weeks from the NW-central region of the JLP. Most samples were collected within the boundaries of two mapping regions. Specifically, six samples were collected in the graduate mapping region (Fig. 9), seven were collected in the undergraduate mapping region (Fig. 10), and four were collected along the sizeable Kqd pendant to the south of both mapping regions (Fig. 6).

9.1.2. Undergraduate Mapping Region

Between the six samples collected within the undergraduate mapping region, there are a few notable patterns in occurrence. Three samples, SU 82 A, SU 82 B, and SU 82 BB, were collected from a singular 15m enclave swarm present in a body of Kjr towards the center of the metavolcanics pendant (Km) near the central eastern extent of the mapping region. While there is a slight variation in color, all enclaves present in said swarm appeared to be quartz diorite. Notable attributes included some of the enclaves being rather sizeable, with the largest reaching the size of 2 x 0.5 m, and the presence of needle-like hornblende throughout the swarm. The remainder of the four mafic samples are derived from the northwestern portion of the mapping area along contacts between the Jackass Lakes Granodiorite unit (Kj), the northern occurrence of the Jackass Lakes granodiorite Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr), and the northern extent of the

metavolcanic (Km) pendant. Two of said samples, SU 18 and SU 23, were collected in the Kj outcrop near its contact with the northwest extent of the Km unit along the western extent of Rutherford Lake. Notably, SU 18 was derived from a sizeable meter-scale mafic occurrence present within the enclave swarm (Fig. 11). The third sample, SU 35, was derived from an enclave swarm in the aforementioned Kj outcrop along the eastern extent of Rutherford Lake, near its contact with the Kjr outcrop to the south. The final sample of the undergraduate region, SU 139m, was derived from an outcrop of Kjr containing an enclave swarm within the northeastern extent of the Km outcrop near its contact with the Kjr to the north (Fig. 11). The enclaves present within the swarm showcased varying occurrences of plagioclase phenocrysts and ranged in size from cm- to m-scale, with the largest enclaves being 5 x 2m in size.

9.1.3. Graduate Mapping Region

In comparison to the samples from the undergraduate mapping region, which occurred primarily in two subunits of the granodioritic host, the six samples derived from the graduate mapping region are more varied in occurrence, in the sense that some of the samples were derived from Kqd outcrops. Of the six samples, only two, SM 127 and SM 188m, are derived from bodies within the predominant Kj outcrop of the mapping region, with the other four being derived from Kqd outcrops. Specifically, SM 127 was derived from a mafic enclave swarm within an area of the Kj isolated from any Kqd bodies (Fig. 11), with the only notable attributes being minor variations of the quartz diorite composition of some enclaves and the occasional occurrence of plagioclase phenocrysts and euhedral hornblende. SM 188m was derived in a region of the Kj where a meter scale mafic enclave was present containing even darker mafic enclaves (Fig. 11). Regarding the other four samples from the graduate mapping region, SM 49 is derived from a relatively minor outcrop of Kqd in the southeastern extent of the mapping region along its contact with the adjacent Kja body (Fig. 11). The remaining three samples are derived from outcrops of Kqd relatively adjacent to one another, with SM 156 occurring in a small outcrop of Kqd seemingly mingled with the surrounding Kj (Fig. 11). The remaining two samples, SM 110m and SM 163, are both derived from occurrences of Kqd within a body of Kqd and Kpp alongside one another (Fig. 12). Notably, at both locations, the Kqd and Kpp were intruded by Kj dikes.

9.1.4. Southern Kqd Pendant

The four remaining samples collected outside of the graduate and undergraduate mapping region were sourced in and along a km-scale Kqd pendant located to the south of both mapping regions. SU 191 was sampled from an enclave swarm along the northern extent of the Kqd pendant's contact with the adjacent Kj unit (Fig. 12). Notably, the enclaves present in said swarm all generally appear to be notably more mafic than those present at swarms that lack the occurrence of a Kqd outcrop. SU 192 was also collected along the contact of the Kqd's northern extent and the surrounding Kj (Fig. 12). However, mingling with the Kj unit was much more prominent at this location than the location SU 191 was collected from. Samples 193A and 193B are derived from a location in the southeastern extent of the Kqd pendant (Fig. 12). The varying occurrence of veining and mm- to cm-scale feldspar phenocrysts in select spots alludes to extensive mingling in said area.

9.2. Petrography

9.2.1. Mineralogy

While the various hand samples seemed compositionally homogeneous, mineral abundances present in the nineteen mafic thin sections demonstrate some degree of heterogeneity. The major minerals present include plagioclase feldspar, quartz, hornblende, biotite, and alkali feldspar, with said five minerals being typical for intermediate granitoids. The minor minerals present include sphene, apatite, chlorite, epidote, and opaque minerals such as magnetite and hematite. With the mineral abundances of each thin section present (Fig. 13, Table 2), it becomes apparent how certain minerals vary more in occurrence between the nineteen compositions present. Namely, quartz varies the most with a range of 3-30%, with hornblende and plagioclase feldspar being tied as the second most varied mineral with their respective ranges of 14-40% and 29-55%, and biotite has a range of 5-25%. While of the five major minerals, alkali feldspar varies the least in occurrence with a range of only 15%, it is distinct in the sense that it is the only major mineral that is completely absent in some of the thin sections (Fig. 13, Table 2). Namely, no alkali feldspar is present in samples SU 35, SM 188m, SU 82A, SU 82B, SU 82BB, and SU 193B.

9.2.2. Rock textures and microstructures

Across all thin sections, plagioclase grains are euhedral to slightly subhedral, and showcase both albite and Carlsbad twinning (Fig. 14). Alongside twinning, plagioclase feldspar grains also frequently showcase predominantly oscillatory zoning and normal zoning (Fig. 14). Biotite across all thin sections appear euhedral to somewhat anhedral, and largely lack the occurrence of birds-eye extinction. Similarly, hornblende also varies from euhedral to anhedral in occurrence. Various hornblende grains showcase single twins (Fig. 14), with some also showcasing pleochroic zoning, typically characterized by more brown-green cores and green-yellow rims (Fig. 14). Given their relatively similar appearance and shared showcasing of poikilitic textures (Fig. 14) along with plagioclase feldspar, quartz and alkali feldspar are somewhat difficult to distinguish, with their most distinct attributes being differences in birefringence, their lack of albite twinning and normal zoning, the occurrence of myrmekite texture (Fig. 15) and undulatory extinction in quartz, and the occasional occurrence of microcline and Carlsbad twinning in alkali feldspar, along occasional showcasing of perthite in some thin sections.

Most of the mafic samples are porphyritic, with plagioclase feldspar likely deriving from the granodioritic host. Plagioclase feldspar varies the most in grain size, ranging from roughly 0.20 to 20 mm. In various thin sections, multiple plagioclase grains occur in close enough proximity to one another to the point where they occasionally form plagioclase clusters. The largest observed plagioclase cluster occurred in SU 35 and was measured to be roughly 0.5 x 0.5 cm (Fig. 15). Sericitization can be observed occurring in plagioclase grains within nearly every thin section. While the degree of sericitization can vary between grain to grain in each thin section, it almost exclusively occurs in the cores of plagioclase grains (Fig. 15), alluding to higher An-content present in the earlier occurrences of the mafic magma. Depending on the thin section, sphene occurs as euhedral to subhedral, with some occurrences showcasing the mineral's characteristic wedge-like shape (Fig. 15). In addition to frequently occurring textures and microstructures, there are also some textures and microstructures only observed in a select few thin sections. Most notably, in addition to showcasing the largest observed plagioclase clusters, SU 35 also showcased the only observed occurrence of quartz miarolitic cavities (Fig. 15), which at their largest are roughly 3 x 4 mm in size. Furthermore, in contrast to all other thin sections, the hornblende and biotite present in SM 188m occurs as a web of clustering grains (Fig. 15).

9.3. Plagioclase Composition

9.3.1. Thin Section Selection

Of the eighteen mafic thin sections, only five were selected to undergo plagioclase composition analysis. Said thin sections, SU 18, SU 82BB, SU 191, SM 49, and SM 156-A1, were selected due to the locations of their respective mafic outcrops. In addition to being relatively spread out with respect to one another, with SU 18 and SU 82BB occurring in mafic outcrops present in the undergraduate mapping region (Fig. 10), SM 49 and SM 156-A1 occurring in mafic outcrops present in the graduate mapping region (Fig. 9), and SU 191 occurring in the large Kqd outcrop to the south of both mapping regions (Fig. 6), they also provided coverage regarding associated subunits. Namely, SU 18's associated outcrop occurs in a body of K_j near its contact with the northmost K_m limb present in the mapping area, SU 82BB's outcrop occurring in a small occurrence of K_{jr} within the central region of the same K_m body, SU 191 originating from the northmost fingering extent of the aforementioned Kqd outcrop, SM 49 occurring in a Kqd outcrop in contact with both K_{ja} on its northern extent and K_j along its southern extent, and SM 156-A1 occurring in a small outcrop of Kqd surrounded by K_j and other Kqd outcrops. It should be noted that of the two compositions present in SM 156-A1, only the coarser-grained composition was examined for plagioclase feldspar composition, as the finer-grained composition lacked enough plagioclase feldspar grains that clearly showcased albite twinning. Samples SU 16 IIL of K_j and SU 127 of K_{jr} were selected to compare mafic outcrop plagioclase composition with that of the two host granodiorite subunits associated with mafic outcrops.

9.3.2. Anorthite Percentages

Overall, the five mafic samples showcase relatively uniform anorthite content. Specifically, SU 18 showcases an average anorthite percentage of 40%, SM 49 showcases an anorthite percentage of 43%, SU 191 showcases an anorthite percentage of 43.5%, SM 156 showcases an anorthite percentage of 44%, and SU 82BB showcases an anorthite percentage of 45%, indicating that that the five samples only show 5% variability in plagioclase composition. In contrast, the granodioritic host samples showcase much lower and widespread anorthite percentage values, with SU 16 IIL yielding an anorthite percentage of 25.5% and SU 127 showcasing an anorthite percentage of 13.5% (Fig. 16; Table 3). It should be noted that for both

granodioritic host samples, the extinction angles were plotting low enough on the extinction angle-plagioclase composition diagram (Fig. 8) that they each possessed two potential anorthite percentage values. As such, the plagioclase grains of each thin section had their relief compared to that of the surrounding epoxy via movement of the Becke line to determine which of the two values to use. In sum, there is a 12% difference in plagioclase composition between the two observed granodioritic host subunits, and a 14% difference between the lowest of the mafic sample anorthite values and the higher of the two granodioritic host values.

9.4. Cathodoluminescence (CL) Microscopy

9.4.1. Thin Section Selection

Of the seventeen mafic samples, only samples SU 35, SM 156-A1, and SU 192 underwent cathodoluminescence microscopy. SM 156-A1 was selected due to the presence of two mingled rock compositions in its thin section (Fig. 17). SU 35 and SU 192 were both selected for CL microscopy primarily due to their sizeable plagioclase grains making zoning analysis easier. For all three thin sections, emphasis was placed on identifying any notable mineral zoning in plagioclase grains that could be used as a marker of mixed plagioclase populations between the enclave and host magma.

9.4.2. SU 192

Sample SU 192 (Fig. 18) contains multiple large grains of bright blue luminescing alkali feldspar. This samples also contains the most plagioclase grains with visible zoning, as many of the smaller plagioclase grains demonstrate alternating bands of red and green coloration, which represent alternating bands of sodic and calcic rich plagioclase, respectively. While grains of varying sizes ranging from 0.09 x 0.14 mm at the smallest to 5.04 x 2.78mm at the largest, showcase various degrees of alterations in and around their cores, it is evident that there is a distinction between the larger and smaller zoned plagioclase grains. Specifically, most of the larger grains, which range from 3.79 x 2.57mm to 5.04 x 2.78mm in size, appear to have greenish (calcic) cores whereas most of the smaller grains, which range from 0.09 x 0.14 mm to 0.12 x 0.16 mm in size, seem to have reddish (sodic) cores. Notably, in most of the smaller grains with sodic cores, there is usually one primary ring of calcic plagioclase in relatively close proximity to the cores.

9.4.3. SM 156-A1

Sample SM 156-A1 (Fig. 19) exposes two mingled magmatic rocks separated by a sharp contact. In both rock compositions of the thin section, there is little to no alkali feldspar present. Within the finer-grained portion of the thin section, zoned plagioclase grains are much less abundant, with most plagioclase occurring as tiny grains ranging in size from 0.04 x 0.06mm to 0.76 x 0.58 mm possessing relatively uniform pinkish-orange coloration and no zoning. However, in the larger grains, ranging from 0.59 x 1.30mm to 7.09 x 3.55mm, oscillatory zoning is occasionally present, with their cores generally being more bluish in coloration whereas their rims are more pinkish. In the coarser-grained side, oscillatory zoning was present even in the smallest of grains, some of which were as small as 0.86 x 1.86mm. While many of the zoned grains display a coloration pattern similar to that of the finer-grained side, some grains have cores that are distinctly green-yellow rather than bluish. Notably, while there are a select few grains on the finer-grained side with cores more greenish than blue, they are far less present and sizeable than those present on the coarser-grained side of the thin section.

9.4.4. SU 35

Sample SU 35 (Fig. 20) has the largest plagioclase grains of the three samples that underwent CL microscopy. Furthermore, SU 35 is the only sample of the three that showcases clustering of larger plagioclase grains, which range from 0.47 x 1.14mm to 3.10 x 5.88mm in size. Even with the occurrence of sericitization in the cores of many of the clustered plagioclase grains, it is evident that most zoned grains possess more bluish cores and pink rims, indicating a shift in composition from calcic to sodic. Whereas the zoning in the grains of the two other CL images is comparatively sharp and easily identifiable, the shift from the bluish cores to the pinker rim layers in these plagioclase phenocrysts is much more irregular than ring-like. Such a phenomenon is more apparent in clustered plagioclase grains than in the few singular large plagioclase grains present, which appear to have more sharp and consistent zoning. In addition to the plagioclase clustering, the CL image confirms the occurrence of quartz miarolitic cavities in said thin section, with said cavities taking on a dark purple coloration as is typical for quartz in CL.

9.5. XRF Whole Rock Data Analysis

9.5.1. Overview

The complete major oxide and trace element concentrations of the seventeen mafic samples are presented in Table 4. As per the data (Fig. 21; Table 4), the major oxides present include SiO₂, TiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MnO, MgO, CaO, Na₂O, K₂O, P₂O₅, and FeOt. The trace elements include Rb, Sr, Ba, Zr, Y, Nb, Cs, Sc, V, Cr, Ni, CU, Zn, Ga, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Hf, Pb, Th, and U (Figs. 22-24; Table 4). Particular emphasis was placed on major oxides MgO, FeOt, CaO, and trace elements Ba, Sr, and Zr, with a second said of plots being made with said major oxides and trace elements incorporating the data of both mafic and granodioritic host samples for comparison (Fig. 25). As made apparent in the plot legend (Fig. 21- 25), samples were divided in accordance with their respective mafic outcrops' associated units, that of which being the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj), the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr), and the quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd)

9.5.2. Data Trends

When identified using the Middlemost (1994) rock classification diagram, most samples plot in diorite and gabbroic diorite, with two samples, SU 139m and SU 35, plotting in the monzonite region (Fig. 26). As evident in some major oxide and trace element plots, the mafic samples do not always group together in accordance with unit type. Namely, in the MgO vs. SiO₂ plot (Fig. 21), one Kj sample and two Kjr samples increase the range of mafic samples along the y-axis. In the FeOt vs. SiO₂ plot incorporating all samples (Fig. 25), two Kqd samples showcasing the lowest silica extent of all samples also have the highest FeOt values of all samples and are notably removed from even the other mafic samples. In the Sr vs. SiO₂ plot incorporating all samples (Fig. 25), one Kjr sample is relatively removed from the three other Kjr samples, which all plot on the higher Sr extent of the JLP compositions.

In each of the plots, and as expected, the mafic samples generally occupy the low silica extent of compositions in the JLP. In the three major oxide plots incorporating host rock data (Fig. 25), the mafic points all generally follow the trend produced by the host points. Such is also observed in the Sr vs. SiO₂ plot (Fig. 25), in which the mafic points generally follow the trend produced by the host rock points, albeit much less strictly. In contrast, the two remaining trace element plots (Fig. 25) incorporating host rock data both showcase varied distribution of points even among the host magma samples.

10. Discussion

While the seventeen samples are derived from mafic enclaves throughout the JLP, they display relatively uniform mineral compositions and share various textures. This, along with all observed mafic enclaves occurring in or in association with two specific granodioritic host phases allude to the possibility of a shared magma source. However, there are some attributes that vary between the samples. Mafic enclaves within the central Sierra Nevada are recognized for bulk compositional diversity and textural variations while simultaneously possessing significant mineralogical and geochemical similarities (Barbarin, 2005, Yoshinobu et al., 2009). The variations within said mafic samples are prominent enough to potentially be attributed to interactions with surrounding granodioritic host rock. Namely, given that mafic inclusions in the JLP are much less likely to possess alkali feldspar (Bateman 1992), the relatively consistent presence of said mineral across the mafic samples collected strongly alludes to the mafic bodies incorporating components of the granodioritic host phases via enclave-host exchange (Barnes et al., 2021). Furthermore, some of the samples that originated from the same mafic outcrop and in extremely close proximity to one another showcase variations in mineral abundances, textures, and geochemical composition. While some of said variation within individual outcrops could potentially be explained by their respective enclave swarms forming from the breakup of heterogeneous dikes (Tobisch et al., 1997), it is also possible that said enclave swarms simply represent the disaggregation of synplutonic dikes (McNulty et al., 1996), in which subsequent variations in enclave composition could potentially be attributed to the integration of surrounding granodioritic host components during the mingling and disaggregation process.

The plagioclase of the five mafic samples selected for the Michel Lévy method showcased extremely similar average anorthite contents to one another, ranging only from 40 to 45% anorthite. Such homogeneity in plagioclase composition strongly alludes to the associated mafic bodies sharing a singular source, as if the various mafic bodies were to be derived from various mafic sources, they likely would have showcased more varied plagioclase compositions.

Given that they are structurally and compositionally different enough to be considered two distinct phases, it is expected for the K_j and K_{jr} units to showcase more variability in plagioclase composition (13.5% anorthite and 25.5% anorthite). Their more varied plagioclase compositions, compounded with the fact that their anorthite range is significantly lower than the

mafic sample anorthite range, not only endorse the idea that the mafic samples are much more compositionally uniform but also imply that interaction between the mafic magmas and their associated granodioritic host phases must have been relatively limited. If significant interaction between the two were to have occurred, the average anorthite contents of the various mafic samples would be much more varied and likely closer to the values of the host samples.

In the CL image of SM 156-A1, it is apparent that while the contact between the two units is not completely solid, there was not significant mineral grain trading between the two units. The irregular transition between the more sodic and calcic plagioclase observed in plagioclase grains of SU 35 can be attributed to the plagioclase in the cores being in disequilibrium with a secondary melt that occurred. The relatively sudden occurrence of the notable shift in melt composition alludes to it being the result of the incorporation of more felsic components into the melt at a certain point in its history rather than the result of the depletion of certain minerals in the melt as it gradually solidified over time. While only observed directly via CL microscopy in SU 35, the zoning of select plagioclase grains in other samples sometimes appear irregular when observed under cross polarized light, implying that infiltrating melt from host magma was not isolated to SU 35's sample location.

Both major oxide and trace element data point towards compositional variety existing between the mafic samples. While in general the mafic samples plot along the trend line produced by the data from all related samples, there are notable occurrences of variability for some major oxides and trace elements. While much more minor when compared to distribution in the trace element plots, the three major oxide plots all showcase the mafic samples as being more widely distributed than the felsic samples, as seen by how the outlines of sample distribution for each major oxide plot tends to bulge and become more irregular around the mafic samples in comparison to regions where only the felsic samples plot.

Even when observing solely mafic samples, samples with the same unit association are relatively dispersed from one another in various major oxide and trace element plots, with even relative mineral abundances being unable to fully account for such distribution. The scatter of Ba and Sr values allude to feldspar variations which may in part be attributed to varied occurrences in phenocrysts throughout the samples. Occurrences in which samples have relatively similar SiO₂ values but varied distributions on the vertical scale may be indicative of accumulation.

Such is observed in the Zr vs. SiO₂ plot (Fig. 22), which implies zircon accumulation. The classification of samples SU 139m and SU 35 as monzonite is possibly the result of feldspars from the host magma being incorporated into the enclaves. Such a lack of grouping in major oxide, trace element plots, and rock classification clearly represents variation and heterogeneity in mafic sample compositions. Said heterogeneity in turn can be related to the incorporation of surrounding granodioritic host phases via magma mixing/mingling, as well as the mafic outcrops experiencing varying levels of melt loss (Barnes et al., 2021).

11. Conclusions

There are numerous uniform attributes across the mafic samples that emphasize the homogeneity of mafic bodies within the JLP, such as their uniform plagioclase composition, similar modal abundances, and shared petrographic structure, which indicate they likely originated from a shared source. However, as made apparent by attributes such as geochemical variances between samples and evidence of melt compositional changes in CL microscopy, the mafic bodies of the JLP have experienced magma mingling at some point(s) in their existence. Most notably, the geochemical variances found between the samples indicate the occurrence of magma mixing/mingling between some mafic outcrops and surrounding granodioritic host rock. With confirmation of interactions between mafic magmas with more silicic magmas of the JLP, it may be possible for future works to better correlate the occurrence of such interactions with periods of volcanic activity brought about by the remobilization of felsic magmas, and potentially apply said correlations to systems active in the modern day.

12. References

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13. Figures

Figure 1: The general overview of the Jackass Lake Pluton and its location within the Sierra Nevada Batholith (McNulty et al., 1996).

Figure 2: A closer view of the Jackass Lake Pluton and the units that partially segment it into four lobes (Pignotta et al., 2010).

Figure 3: An example of late-phase diorite dikes cutting into the granodioritic host of the Jackass Lake Pluton (McNulty et al., 1996).

Figure 4: An example of mafic sheets observed in the Jackass Lake Pluton (Pignotta et al., 2010).

Figure 5: A general overview of the intrusive suites of Washburn Lake, Merced Peak, and Buena Vista Crest (Bateman, 1992).

Figure 6: Map showcasing the full extent of the Jackass Lakes Pluton (JLP), Undergraduate Mapping Area (outlined in blue), Graduate Mapping Area (outlined in red), and outcrops and sample locations of Kqd (purple). Kqd unit extent added from Peck (1980). Map modified from Yoshinobu et al. (2009).

Figure 7: Illustration of how measuring the two extinction angles of a plagioclase grain as per the Michel Lévy method appears via microscopic view (Nesse 2000).

Figure 8: Diagram utilized to correlate maximum extinction angles with their respective plagioclase anorthite compositions. The dashed curve represents high (volcanic) plagioclase, and the solid curve represents low (plutonic) plagioclase. Diagram curves are based on the curves of Tobi and Kroll, 1975.

Figure 9: Graduate mapping region with mafic sample locations indicated by yellow markers (Map modified from Dunn 2023).

Figure 10: Undergraduate mapping region with mafic sample locations indicated by yellow markers (Map modified from Durning 2023).

Figure 11: Images of various sampled mafic outcrops. A) The enclave swarm SU 18 is derived from. It showcases meter scale occurrences of mafic rock. B) The enclave swarm SU 139m is derived from. C) The enclave swarm SM 127 is derived from. It notably is not associated with any Kqd outcrop. D) The enclave swarm SM 188m is derived from. Notably, the enclaves present showcase two distinct mafic compositions. E) The Kqd outcrop SM 49 is derived from. SM 49 was sampled near the Kqd outcrop's contact with the adjacent Kja unit. F) The relatively small Kqd outcrop SM 156 is derived from. Said outcrop is completely surrounded by Kj.

Figure 12: Images of various sampled mafic outcrops (cont.). A) The outcrop SM 163 is derived from. It is made distinct by the occurrence of Kpp alongside Kqd. B) The enclave swarm SU 191 is derived from. It is in the Kj unit along the northern extent of the major Kqd pendant. C) The Kqd outcrop SU 192 is derived from. Specifically, said outcrop is part of the northern extent of the major Kqd pendant. D) The Kqd outcrop SU 193A and SU 193B are derived from. Specifically, said outcrop is part of the southeastern extent of the major Kqd pendant.

Figure 13: Chart showcasing the overall mineral distributions color-coded of all eighteen thin sections derived from seventeen mafic samples. Samples are organized according to unit. Legend showcases the ranges of all minerals present from all samples.

Figure 14: Mineral textures/ structures in thin section. A) The occurrence of albite twinning in various plagioclase grains in SU 23. B) Carlsbad twinning in a plagioclase grain (lower center) in SM 49. C) Multiple plagioclase grains with normal and oscillatory zoning in SU 191. D) Hornblende grain (upper left) with single twins in SM 49. E) Hornblende grain with zoning in SU 193B. F) Various plagioclase grains showcasing poikilitic texture in SM 127.

Figure 15: Mineral textures and structures in thin section (cont.). A) Myrmekite texture along the edges of a quartz albite grain in SU 23. B) Plagioclase grain cluster present in SU 35. C) Sericitization occurrence in the core of a plagioclase grain in SU 82BB. D) Wedge-shaped sphene grain in SM 110. E) Quartz-filled miarolitic cavity in SU 35. F) Web-like occurrence of hornblende and biotite grains in SM 188m.

Figure 16: Distribution of the anorthite percentages present in selected thin Section. Mafic samples include SU 18, SM 156 (coarse half), SU 82BB, SU 191, and SM 49. Granodioritic host samples include SU 127 (Kjr phase) and SU 16 IIL (Kj phase).

Figure 17: Showcasing of the two mafic compositions present in SM 156-A1 via the rock chip utilized to make the SM 156-A1 thin section.

Figure 18: Cathodoluminescence image of thin section SU 192. Scale in bottom right corner of image. Note the relatively high occurrence of alkali feldspar (represented by blue coloration) and plagioclase feldspar grains showing varying core-rim compositions. A reddish-pink coloration indicates sodic plagioclase, a greenish-blue coloration indicates more calcic plagioclase, dark purple indicates quartz, gold indicates apatite, and blue indicates alkali feldspar. Minerals such as hornblende, biotite, hematite, and magnetite appear black due to their lack of luminescence.

Figure 19: Cathodoluminescence image of thin section SM 156-A1. Scale in bottom right corner of image. Note the presence of two mafic compositions and the sharp, notable lack of mineral grain trading along their contact. A reddish-pink coloration indicates sodic plagioclase, a greenish-blue coloration indicates more calcic plagioclase, dark purple indicates quartz, gold indicates apatite, and blue indicates alkali feldspar. Minerals such as hornblende, biotite, hematite, and magnetite appear black due to their lack of luminescence.

Figure 20: Cathodoluminescence image of thin section SU 35. Scale in bottom right corner of image. Note the occurrence of irregular plagioclase zoning in clustered plagioclase grains, high amounts of sericitization in the cores of clustered plagioclase grains, and the presence of miarolitic cavities throughout the thin section. A reddish-pink coloration indicates sodic plagioclase, a greenish-blue coloration indicates more calcic plagioclase, dark purple indicates quartz, gold indicates apatite, and blue indicates alkali feldspar. Minerals such as hornblende, biotite, hematite, and magnetite appear black due to their lack of luminescence.

Multiple plot of SiO₂ vs. TiO₂, Al₂O₃, MgO, MnO, CaO, Na₂O, K₂O, P₂O₅, FeOt

Figure 21: Major oxide concentrations vs. SiO₂ plots of the mafic samples. Axes in wt. %.

Legend provided and consistent with all XRF plots present. Units represented in legend include the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj), the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr) and the Quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd).

Multiple plot of SiO₂ vs. Rb, Sr, Ba, Zr, Y, Nb, Cs, Sc

Figure 22: Trace element concentrations vs. SiO₂ plots of the mafic samples. Horizontal axis in wt. %. Vertical axis in ppm. Legend provided and consistent with all XRF plots present. Units represented in legend include the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj), the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr) and the Quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd).

Multiple plot of SiO₂ vs. V, Cr, Ni, Cu, Zn, Ga, La

Figure 23: Trace element concentrations vs. SiO₂ plots of the mafic samples (cont.). Horizontal axis in wt. %. Vertical axis in ppm. Legend provided and consistent with all XRF plots present. Units represented in legend include the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj), the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr) and the Quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd).

Multiple plot of SiO₂ vs. Ce, Pr, Nd, Hf, Pb, Th, U

Figure 24: Trace element concentrations vs. SiO₂ plots of the mafic samples (cont.). Horizontal axis in wt. %. Vertical axis in ppm. Legend provided and consistent with all XRF plots present. Units represented in legend include the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj), the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr) and the Quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd).

Figure 25: Major oxide (top row) and trace element (bottom row) plots vs. SiO₂ of both mafic and granodioritic host samples. The distribution of data points from granodioritic host samples is represented by the blue outlines present in each plot. Vertical axes in wt.% (major oxides) and ppm (trace elements). Horizontal axes in wt.% (all six plots). Legend provided and consistent with all XRF plots present. Units represented in legend include the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj), the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (KjR) and the Quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd).

Figure 26: Whole rock geochemical classification of the JLP mafic samples. Classification based on Middlemost (1994). Units represented in legend include the Jackass Lakes granodiorite phase (Kj), the Jackass Lakes Rutherford Lake phase (Kjr) and the Quartz diorite and tonalite unit (Kqd).

14. Data Tables

Sample Number	Unit	Surrounding Unit	UTM Sample Location		Sample Type
			Easting	Northing	
SU 23	Kj	Kj	11S 0290504	4163797	enclave
SU 192	Kj	Kj	11S 0292758	4160820	larger kqd body
SU 18	Kj	Kj	11S 0291136	4163949	enclave
SU 35	Kj	Kj	11S 0290814	4163528	enclave
SM 127	Kj	Kj	11S 0291979	4164337	enclave
SM 188 (m)	Kj	Kj	11S 0290853	4164918	enclave
SU 139 (m)	Kjr	Km	11S 0291912	4163220	enclave
SU 82A	Kjr	Km	11S 0291955	4162514	enclave
SU 82B	Kjr	Km	11S 0291955	4162514	enclave
SU 82BB	Kjr	Km	11S 0291955	4162514	enclave
SM 163	Kqd	Kqd	11S 0293106	4165533	larger kqd body
SM 110 (m)	Kqd	Kqd	11S 0293140	4165693	larger kqd body
SU 191	Kqd	Kqd	11S 0292407	4161088	enclave
SU 193B	Kqd	Kqd	11S 0294927	4158745	larger kqd body
SU 193A	Kqd	Kqd	11S 0294927	4158745	larger kqd body
SM 156	Kqd	Kj	11S 0293671	4164817	larger kqd body
SM 49	Kqd	Kqd	11S 0293850	4163284	larger kqd body

Table 1: Mafic sample location data and associated units.

Sample #	Unit	Plagioclase Feldspar	Quartz	Hornblende	Biotite	Alkali Feldspar	Sphene	Trace Minerals (Apatite, Chlorite, and Epidote)	Opaque Minerals	Total
SU 23	Kj	42	20	18	12	5	1	0.99	1	99.99
SU 192	Kj	35	12	15	19	15	2	0.99	1	99.99
SU 18	Kj	37	23	25	5	7	0.1	0.9	2	100
SU 35	Kj	30	25	23	20	0	0.5	0.99	0.5	99.99
SM 127	Kj	35	30	20	5	6	1	0.99	2	99.99
SM 188m	Kj	45	3	40	10	0	0.5	0.99	0.5	99.99
SU 139m	Kjr	40	28	20	5	2	1	2	2	100
SU 82A	Kjr	30	22	25	20	0	1	0.99	1	99.99
SU 82B	Kjr	29	24	25	20	0	0.5	0.99	0.5	99.99
SU 82BB	Kjr	30	20	25	23	0	0.5	0.99	0.5	99.99
SM 163	Kqd	40	13	15	20	8	1	0.99	2	99.99
SM 110m	Kqd	35	25	17	18	2	1	0.99	1	99.99
SU 191	Kqd	40	27	14	11	5	1	0.99	1	99.99
SU 193A	Kqd	36	10	25	25	1	1	0.99	1	99.99
SU 193B	Kqd	55	5	15	20	0	2	0.99	2	99.99
SM 156-A	Kqd	40	20	15	17	5	1	0.99	1	99.99
SM 156-A1 (Top)	Kqd	40	22	16	15	2	2	0.99	2	99.99
SM 156-A1 (Bottom)	kqd	35	11	30	20	2	0	0.99	1	99.99
SM 49	Kqd	35	20	22	18	2	1	0.99	1	99.99

Table 2: Modal Abundances of the nineteen compositions present in the eighteen mafic-based thin sections.

Sample Number	Grain 1 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 2 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 3 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 4 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 5 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 6 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 7 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 8 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 9 Avg. Extinction Angle	Grain 10 Avg. Extinction Angle	Anorthite (An) Percentage
SU 18	11.5°	17.25°	13.75°	17.25°	13.5°	11.875°	14.75°	17°	21.5°	14.75°	40%
SM 156 (coarse)	23.625°	21.25°	16.125°	8.75°	15°	22°	15.75°	19.375°	17.5°	10.25°	44%
SU 82BB	19.75°	17.5°	14°	24.75°	18.25°	16.75°	16°	17.375°	22°	17°	45%
SU 191	15°	19.75°	23.5°	10°	11.75°	14.375°	16.375°	14°	10.25°	13.5°	43.5%
SM 49	16°	13°	22°	23°	22°	9°	21.125°	10.25°	11.5°	22.25°	43%
SU 127	6°	5.75°	6.75°	8.5°	7°	6.25°	4.75°	6.5°	7.75°	7.25°	13.5%
SU 16 ILL	8.375°	8°	7.875°	9.25°	8.25°	6°	8.75°	9.5°	4.125°	6.75°	25.5%

Table 3: The ten average albite twinning extinction angles and average anorthite percentage of the thin sections studied using the Michel Lévy method. **Bolded** values are the highest extinction angle values measured in each section that were used to calculate the average anorthite percentages of each thin section.

Sample Number	SU 23	SU 192	SU 18	SU 35	SM 127	SM 188 (m)	SU 139 (m)	SU 82A	SU 82B	SU 82BB	SM 163	SM 110 (m)	SU 191	SU 193B	SU 193A	SM 156	SM 49
Unit	Kj	Kj	Kj	Kj	Kj	Kj	Kjr	Kjr	Kjr	Kjr	Kgd	Kgd	Kgd	Kgd	Kgd	Kgd	Kgd
SiO2	61.78	61.67	57.51	58.05	59.84	56.47	57.58	58.63	57.96	58.01	56.99	57.99	59.73	53.46	54.18	59.12	57.41
TiO2	0.9	0.85	1.21	1.01	1.1	1.06	1.1	0.9	0.88	0.85	1.18	1.11	0.93	1.26	1.16	0.98	1.1
Al2O3	16.86	16.89	17.58	17.22	17.42	17.49	18.96	17.43	17.26	17.22	18.18	17.61	17.39	19.04	18.5	18.22	18.55
Fe2O3	6.27	6.61	7.52	7.16	6.42	7	6.5	5.69	6.66	6.82	8.12	7.46	7.11	9.66	9.42	6.99	6.96
MnO	0.13	0.11	0.14	0.14	0.18	0.12	0.18	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.13	0.13	0.11	0.16	0.15	0.11	0.12
MgO	2.33	2.47	3.12	3.6	2.56	4.66	2.56	4.62	4.61	4.59	3.26	3.31	2.8	3.61	3.97	2.48	3.43
CaO	5.15	5.13	6.59	6.11	5.82	8.55	6.42	6.91	6.84	6.74	6.26	6.74	5.87	7.11	7.19	5.86	7.37
Na2O	4.36	3.42	4.26	5.23	4.91	2.51	4.3	3.41	3.41	3.21	3.48	3.29	3.5	3.46	3.24	3.31	3.02
K2O	1.81	2.42	1.55	1.06	1.28	1.65	1.92	1.75	1.72	1.9	1.88	1.89	2.14	1.71	1.68	2.4	1.65
P2O5	0.22	0.22	0.29	0.24	0.26	0.24	0.27	0.31	0.31	0.29	0.3	0.24	0.21	0.27	0.3	0.28	0.22
Total	99.79	99.76	99.76	99.82	99.78	99.75	99.78	99.74	99.74	99.73	99.76	99.76	99.71	99.73	99.76	99.73	99.79
Rb	81	95	54	57	55	74	92	53	54	61	78	84	80	60	59	86	70
Sr	468	481	595	493	608	574	572	798	802	786	703	697	520	599	569	628	538
Ba	591	815	674	314	441	615	575	649	633	697	669	644	695	820	695	890	514
Zr	127	163	159	124	154	134	132	98	100	112	146	119	153	224	157	206	114
Y	28	19	21	14	33	19	26	8	8	9	15	14	18	29	21	20	16
Nb	10	6	6	6	11	4	7	0	0	0	3	2	5	7	4	7	5
Cs	0	0	0	7	5	3	9	0	0	0	3	7	0	2	3	2	0
Sc	14	15	17	15	16	21	18	17	16	21	15	17	15	19	21	14	18
V	139	124	181	149	151	180	127	129	125	132	155	173	147	188	189	118	190
Cr	4	4	9	48	1	99	0	113	116	116	5	10	4	6	5	3	23
Ni	0	0	8	28	0	24	1	47	47	48	7	7	2	4	4	0	4
Cu	11	12	22	9	11	6	14	21	20	30	11	10	14	15	12	20	22
Zn	92	90	98	103	114	90	128	107	109	104	112	108	89	117	109	96	92
Ga	22	22	23	23	24	22	24	23	22	22	24	24	21	25	22	24	23
La	32	29	20	25	39	25	26	20	17	17	14	25	26	22	21	25	15
Ce	65	57	59	47	87	72	55	41	50	47	52	44	60	64	50	50	40
Pr	9	7	8	7	10	7	8	7	5	7	8	5	6	6	8	8	5
Nd	25	23	22	17	37	32	20	15	20	17	19	16	24	26	19	19	14
Hf	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	3	4	5	4	5	3
Pb	16	17	15	17	23	21	16	14	15	16	12	14	17	14	12	15	11
Th	8	13	6	3	7	6	7	6	6	6	7	6	10	5	6	8	6
U	4	5	4	2	3	2	4	3	1	2	4	4	4	3	3	3	1

Table 4: Whole-rock XRF analysis data consisting of major oxide (wt.%) and trace element concentrations (ppm) of mafic samples from the Jackass Lakes Pluton.